
Recognition of Construction Contract Revenue based on PSAK 34 at PT Tunggal Jaya Raya

Firdaus Indra Faradiba¹, Sulis Rochayatun²

¹⁾ Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic Univeristy Malang, Gajayana St. No. 50, Lowokwaru, Malang, 65144, East Java, Indonesia

Email: firdausfaradiba98@gmail.com

²⁾ Maulana Malik Ibrahim State Islamic Univeristy Malang, Gajayana St. No. 50, Lowokwaru, Malang, 65144, East Java, Indonesia

Email: sulis@uin-malang.ac.id

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ABSTRACT

All companies have the aim to get profit with maximum. One of the elements related to the acquisition of profit is income. In each type of company certainly have different methods in recognizing its income. In the construction company there are two ways of revenue recognition namely completion percentage and contract completion. This research aims to determine how the revenue recognition of the construction contracts used by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya.

This research uses qualitative research methods. The results showed that the company in recognizing its earnings on the basis of cash receipts or cash bases, with a period of 4 months. The company is working on a project with a period of 4 months using the system, but the record is not in accordance with PSAK No. 34.

The conclusion of this research is that the company in recognizing the income of contracts if using recognition by the method of settlement percentage preferably with a cost approach so that the value of income and profit value can be recognized more precisely. However, looking at the project time period of 4 months, the company should use the completed contract method.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recent economic development has spread to various business sectors, starting from services, and other various sectors. The current economic development in various business sectors on both small and large scale can be considered to be very dynamic. It leads the management to be able to take the right opportunities, policies, and strategies to maintain the company's going concern as an effort to stay ahead in market competition. In order to maintain going concern in a company, increasing profit is definitely the main goal, as well as to improve financial performance in a company.

Information needed to examine financial performance using financial reports which is used as a reference in making decisions about policies. one of them is the income statement. Income statement is a report that displays the performance of a company in a period (Martani et al. 2012). In income statement, there are several elements, namely income and expenses.

PSAK No. 23, which discusses income that becomes the main problem in determining the time to recognize income. PSAK No. 23 also describes the measurement of income from sales of goods / services, interest, development, distribution, and disclosure, but the revenue recognition for construction companies is regulated separately in PSAK No. 34.

PSAK No. 34 has the objective of providing guidance on recognizing construction contracts, because the nature and activities of a construction contract which are the execution date and the date of completion of the contract usually happen in different accounting periods. Thus, the main problem in a construction contract is “the allocation of contract revenue and contract costs in the period in which the construction work is carried out” (Gallagher and Andrew 2000; Kustono and Nanggala 2020).. PSAK No. 34 which regulates the recognition of revenue for construction contracts in paragraph 23 states that the recognition of income and expenses must pay attention to the stage of completion of long-term contracts using the percentage of completion method.

Another method, a construction activity which is completed in less than 1 accounting period or less than one year in services and the recognition of revenue and profit is only recognized when the contract is completed. (Kieso et al. 2007). Some of these methods certainly have different effects on the company's financial statements.

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is a private company in the construction sector. This company works on projects from the government. The project undertaken by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is based on an auction process that competes with other tenders. After winning the auction, the company starts working on the project at the stated contract price. It takes less than a year and uses the term system calculation or the percentage completion method. The financial accounting standard states that projects whose recognition uses the term system or the percentage of completion method are contracts that have a term of more than one year (Kustono and Nanggala 2020).

Previous researchers who discussed the accounting for construction income have resulted in several conclusions. There are case of companies applying revenue recognition method which are not in accordance with PSAK No. 34 due to differences between the application of methods in companies

and in financial accounting standards (Febritina, 2019). Relevant to Fitriana (2015), a company applied the construction contract revenue recognition method differently to financial accounting standards. Inversely, there is still study which states that a company has implemented the revenue recognition method in accordance with PSAK No. 34 (Benny, 2016).

Dealing with this phenomenon, it turns out that there are still many construction companies which have not implemented financial accounting standards regarding construction contracts, as well as the companies that are being studied (Yevdokimova et al. 2018). PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is a construction contract company that does not use guidelines in recognizing construction revenue. The company recognizes its income on a flexible basis. PT Tunggal Jaya Raya does not have any specific standard in recognizing its income, thus researchers interested in examining either methods or policies used by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya in recognizing its income.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK AND HYPOTHESES

Definition of Income

Harahap (2011), stated that income is the result of the sale of a good or service and is charged to customers or those who receive these goods and services. The income in PSAK 23 is defined as the gross cash inflow obtained from the economic benefits of the company's normal activities during the accounting period, which causes an increase in inflows and an increase in equity, but the increase does not come from the participation of investors.

Income Recognition

Income recognition is generally recognized on a cash and accrual basis. The recognition of income can be recognized when the revenue has been earned, can be measured, and collectively. Measurement of income here is measured regarding the value of products or services that have a turnover in transactions consisting of net cash or present value. Martani et al. (2012), for the calculation of income and profit in each period, can be seen in the following formula:

<i>Current Period Income / Profit</i>	=	<i>Accumulated revenue (recognized profit)</i>	-	<i>Total Estimated Revenue (until end of the profit period) which has been recognized until the previous period</i>
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Source: Martani et al. (2012)

Construction Contract Revenue Recognition Method

Kieso et al. (2007) states that the income recognition method consists of 2 methods:

a. Contract Method Completed

The completed contract method is the recognition of revenue and gross profit which are recognized when the contract is completed. Costs incurred during the construction process are accumulated in the inventory account or called construction in progress, and the terminals are accumulated in the contra account of inventory, i.e. invoices for construction in process.

b. Completion Percentage Method

Revenues and expenses under this method are recognized on a per accounting period basis. So that the financial statements of a company can show the true value. The assessment is based on the progress of the work. The calculation of the percentage of completion is as follows:

<i>Completion Percentage Method</i>	=	$\frac{\text{Accumulated Costs That Happen to the End}}{\text{Most Recent Estimated Total Cost Period}}$
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Source: (Martani et al. 2012)

The percentage of completion method is also divided into two approaches, physical and cost. The physical approach does not pay attention to the comparative concept, whereas in the cost approach it focuses on the comparative concept. Suwardjono (2011) states that the comparative concept is income in a period which is expensed with costs related to products to generate income.

Construction Contract Revenue Recognition Analysis Based on PSAK No. 34

PSAK No. 34 in paragraph 25 states that the recognition of income and expenses with respect to the stage of completion of a contract is

often referred as the percentage completion method. According to this method, contract revenue is related to contract costs incurred in reaching the completion stage, so that the reported revenue, expenses and profits can be attributed proportionally to the completion of the work.

Paragraph 26 of PSAK No. 34 explains that under the percentage of completion method, contract revenue is recognized as income in income statement in the accounting period in which the work is performed. Contract cost points are usually recognized as an expense in income statement in the accounting period in which the related work is performed. However, any expected difference in total contract costs over total contract revenue should be recognized as an expense according to paragraph 36.

3. RESEARCH METHOD

The approach taken by researchers is a qualitative research approach. Moleong (2014), a qualitative approach is a study that develops descriptive data by using sentences to interpret the phenomena that occur. The research was conducted at a construction service company, PT Tunggal Jaya Raya, which is located in Sidoarjo, East Java. Sources of data in this study are primary data sources and secondary data. Sugiyono (2013) states that primary data is obtained through direct observation and interviews with informants. From these data analysis will be carried out to get a conclusion.

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Application of the Construction Contract Revenue Recognition Method at PT Tunggal Jaya Raya

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya recognizes its revenue on a cash basis or revenue recognition is made when cash is received from customers. The procedure for receiving revenue from customers comes from bills sent by the company to customers, then the cash received by the company goes directly to the company's account. Cash receipts as periodic payments are made without making a transaction journal. Cash received as payment is used and rolled back by the company to carry out its operational activities so there is no journalizing activity.

Project undertaken by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is the construction of a project regarding the

physical construction planning of the Sukodono sub-district building. These development projects have a period of 4 months, from September 2019 to December 2019. During the development process, the company carries out the accounting process by computerizing Microsoft Excel. This company does not use a special accounting application in its recording, including receipt of cash in and receipt of cash out. The basis for the company in recognizing its revenue is based on several data, including through the draft budget, implementation budget design, and data on progress during the construction contract.

Analysis of Construction Contract Revenue Recognition at PT Tunggal Jaya Raya Based on PSAK No. 34

Recognition of revenue from construction contracts for more than 1 accounting period uses the percentage of completion method revenue recognition with two approaches, the physical approach or the cost-to-cost approach. However, the cost to cost approach is preferred because it relates to the concept of the matching principle. Matching principle concept can be defined that between income and expenses must be measured in a balanced manner and must not be focused on either income or expense.

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya carried out the construction of the project which took a short time. However, the company recognizes its revenue using a term system commonly used by long-term projects. In addition, the records used by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya are also not in accordance with PSAK No.34 in the application of the percentage of completion method. The following is a journal recording that should be carried out by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya based on financial accounting standards as follows:

1. Expense journal recording for actual cost:

In Progress Construction Cash/Materials/Depreciation Accumulation/ etc.	XXXX	XXXX
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2. Revenue journal recording of all contracts:

Account Receivables Billing for Construction in Progress	XXXX	XXXX
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3. Payment receipts journal recording of terms:

Cash	XXXX	
Account Receivables		XXXX

4. Revenue recognition journal recording or completion of construction work in month n:

In Progress Construction	XXXX	
Construction Cost	XXXX	
Construction Revenue		XXXX

5. Submission journal recording for the completion of work:

Billing for Construction in Progress	XXXX	
In Progress Construction		XXXX

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya in recognizing its own income regarding expenses and revenues are not recorded according to financial standards or generally accepted regulations. All expenses and income received by the company are directly moved to the company's account without journalizing. It thus indicates that there is no complete information about the completion stage. PT Tunggal Jaya Raya records revenue recognition using the term system method, so that the company must recognize its costs and revenues using the cost to cost method.

In the cost approach, it is related to contract revenue that has been recognized at that time, so that the value of the revenue, expenses, and profit earned can be reported proportionally. According to Martani et al. (2012) there are ways to determine the stage of completion of a construction contract. The formula for expressing the percentage of completion can be done in the following ways:

$$\text{Completion Percentage Method} = \frac{\text{Accumulated Costs That Happen to the End}}{\text{Most Recent Estimated Total Cost Period}}$$

Source: (Martani et al. 2012)

Formula for determining the amount of revenue recognition that must be recognized is as follows:

$$\text{Revenue Recognition} = \text{Completion Percentage} \times \text{Contract Value}$$

Formulas above are used as the basis for calculating revenue recognition using the percentage of completion method. The data needed to perform the calculations above are:

Draft Project Cost Budget and Employer Contract Value (in Rupiah)

No	Work Type	Contract Value in Draft Cost Budget	Employer Contract Value
A.	Preparation Work	19.200.000,00	24.000.000,00
B.	District Office Building Work	4.965.819.351,13	6.207.274.188,92
	Land	32.573.634,94	40.717.0433,67
	Structural	2.345.696.318,32	2.932.120.397,89
	Architectural	2.360.482.790,14	2.950.603.487,67
	Mechanical Electrical	227.066.607,74	283.833.259,68
C	Pendopo Work	503.839.252,29	629.799.065,37
	Land		
	Structural	4.551.001,06	5.688.751,33
	Architectural	277.440.445,34	346.800.556,68
D.		221.847.805,89	277.309.757,36
	Landscape Work	600.758.123,04	750.947.653,80
	Pedestrian	131.969.452,41	164.961.815,52
	Paving Road	390.724.786,77	488.405.983,46
	Fence and Lawn	78.063.883,86	97.579.854,82
Total		6.089.616.726,46	7.612.020.908,08
10% VAT		608.961.672,65	761.202.090,81
Total After Tax		6.698.578.399,11	8.373.222.998,89
Rounded		6.698.578.000,00	8.373.222.000,00

From the data above, it can be determined the size of the completion stage in each month by calculating the progress of the work. Based on the progress and completion stages that have been realized, the company can compare the costs incurred with the most recent overall costs. The following is a calculation regarding the progress or percentage of completion:

Completion Percentage	=	$\frac{\text{Rp } 1.620.386.114,74}{\text{Rp } 6.698.578.399,11} \times 100\%$
	=	24,19%

Based on the calculations above, it can be seen that the percentage of completion in September 2019 is 24.19%. The contract value is calculated at Rp 8,373,222,000, thus the revenue that must be recognized by the company can be formulated as follows:

Revenue Recognition	=	$24,19\% \times \text{Rp } 8.373.222.000$
	=	Rp 2.025.482.643,43

Based on the calculation of revenue recognition, it can be seen that the revenue that must be recognized by the company is Rp 2,025,482,643.43. Construction costs and revenues

that must be recognized are known, so that gross profit can be calculated by subtracting the difference between construction revenue and cost, as follows:

Construction Revenue	Rp 2.025.482.643,43
Construction Cost	Rp 1.620.386.114,74
Profit	Rp 405.096.528,69

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya Construction Contract Revenue Recognition Using the Completion Percentage Method based on PSAK No. 34

The project undertaken by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is the physical construction of the Sukodono sub-district building, where the project runs from September 2019 - December 2019, which is running for 4 months. The following is the cost data incurred each month for the construction of the project as follows:

- Costs incurred during the contract work process:

Project Completion Percentage (in Rupiah)

Month	Cost Budget	Cost Incurred	Percentage *
September	6.698.578.000	1.620.386.114,74	24,19%
October	6.698.578.000	1.623.735.403,94	24,24%
November	6.698.578.000	2.588.330.693,42	38,64%
December	6.698.578.000	866.126.187,00	12,93%
Total			100%

*(Cost Incurred / Cost Budget) x 100%

- Recognition of revenue that must be recognized by the company during the contract work process:

Revenue Recognition (in Rupiah)

Month	Contract Value	Completion Percentage	Revenue
September	8.373.222.000	24,19%	2.025.482.643,43
October	8.373.222.000	24,24%	2.029.669.254,93
November	8.373.222.000	38,64%	3.235.413.366,77
December	8.373.222.000	12,93%	1.082.657.733,76
Total			8.373.222.998,89
Rounded			8.373.222.000,00

The percentage of completion method recognized as value of income in the current period of work. The cost of a construction contract is recognized as an expense in the profit or loss for the period relating to the work in progress. From the journaling process from September 2019 to December 2019, it can be compiled regarding the amount of revenue, total expenses, and the amount of profit recognized in the contract income report in

the physical construction project of the Sukodono sub-district building (attached in Appendix)

PT Tunggal Jaya Raya Construction Contract Revenue Recognition using the Completed Contract Method

Previous revenue recognition uses the completion method. However, the fact that the project undertaken by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is a short-term project of 4 months, then another method that can be used by PT Tunggal Jaya Raya is the completed contract. Unlike the settlement completion recognition method, the completed contract method only costs expenses in each month. However, using the settlement settlement method, it is not only costs that are journalized, but also revenue recognition and accounting. Thus, at the end of December or at the time of delivery of the construction contract, a contract income report for the physical construction project of the Sukodono sub-district building can be prepared as follows:

Contract Revenue	Rp 8.373.222.000
Construction Report	Rp 6.698.578.000
Gross Profit	Rp 1.674.644.000
10% VAT	Rp 152.240.000
Net Profit	Rp 1.522.404.000

Contract revenue report data above shows the company's overall gross profit is Rp 1,674,644,000 which is then reduced by 10% VAT, Rp 152,240,000, so it can be inferred that the company's net profit is Rp 1,522,404,000. The recognition of revenue and recognition of profit between the two methods does have differences. The percentage of completion method for the recognition of profit and income is carried out in stages according to the stage of completion or the percentage of completion. However, the completed contract method recognizes both revenue and profit at the same time when the handover of the contract is completed. This is in line with the previous research (Chowdhury et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2018)

5. CONCLUSION, IMPLICATION, SUGGESTION, AND LIMITATION

Based on the above discussion and analysis, it can be concluded that PT Tunggal Jaya Raya in recording the construction contract revenue recognition method is not in accordance with PSAK No. 34. It is because costs and cash receipts transactions are not recorded. In reality, PT Tunggal Jaya Raya recognizes revenue on a cash basis, but the company does not actually record it on a cash basis. Receipts are only made through an account without journaling. Recognition of revenue on a cash basis reflects the inaccuracy. Receipts on a cash basis are usually determined on the basis of estimates between the two parties, whereas in financial accounting standards it is stated that any revenue recognition transactions should be recognized based on the level of completion of the work.

Based on PSAK No. 34, companies that use the revenue recognition method with a percentage of completion are projects that require long-term development. Considering that the project undertaken by the company is a short-term project, and the company's initial process in recognizing revenue is using the percentage completion method term system, the company must record it in accordance to the standard, PSAK No.34. Recording according to PSAK No.34 is intended so that the historical work that has been completed and everything related to project work can be traced clearly and can be accounted for. In this case, if the company cannot record revenue reliably or the conditions for using the term method are not met, then the company should use the completed contract method in the revenue recognition process for the construction contract.

REFERENCES

Andaki, M. A., J. J. Sondakh, and S. Pinatik. 2015. Analisis perbandingan pengakuan pendapatan dan pembebanan biaya menurut standar akuntansi keuangan dan undang-undang perpajakan pada perusahaan jasa konstruksi (Studi pada PT. Anugrah Adyatama, Jakarta). *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi* 3 (1).

Chen, Y., W. Wang, S. Zhang, and J. You. 2018. Understanding the multiple functions of

- construction contracts: the anatomy of FIDIC model contracts. *Construction Management and Economics* 36 (8):472-485.
- Chowdhury, A. N., P. H. Chen, and R. L. Tiong. 2011. Analysing the structure of public-private partnership projects using network theory. *Construction Management and Economics* 29 (3):247-260.
- Fitriana, E. N. 2015. Analisis Atas Pengakuan Pendapatan Pada Perusahaan Jasa Kontruksi Kaitannya Terhadap Laporan Laba Rugi Perusahaan. *Jurnal Universitas Dian Nswantoro* 2:2-5.
- Gallagher, T. J., and J. D. Andrew. 2000. *Financial management: principles and practice*: Prentice Hall.
- Harahap, S. S. 2011. *Teori Akuntansi, Edisi Revisi, Cetakan Kelima*, PT. Raja Grafindo Perseda, Jakarta. Terjemahan. Edisi Ketujuh. Jakarta: Penerbit Salemba Empat.
- Kieso, D. E., J. J. Weygandt, and T. D. Warfield. 2007. *Akuntansi intermediate jilid 1*. Yogyakarta: Erlangga.
- Kustono, A. S., and A. Y. A. Nanggala. 2020. Preparing quality financial statements at health centers: to explore the role of regional inspectorates and professionalism of accounting personnel. *The Indonesian Accounting Review* 10 (1).
- Martani, D., S. Veronica, R. Wardani, A. Farahmita, and E. Tanujaya. 2012. *Akuntansi Keuangan Menengah Berbasis PSAK*. Jakarta: Salemba Empat.
- Moleong, L. J. 2014. *Metode penelitian kualitatif*. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosdakarya. 2017. *Metode penelitian kualitatif. Cetakan ke 36*, Bandung.
- Oroh, P. C. 2013. Evaluasi Penerapan PSAK No. 34 (Revisi 2010) dalam Pengakuan dan Pengukuran Pendapatan Usaha Jasa Konstruksi pada CV. Surya Gemilang UTAMA. *Jurnal EMBA: Jurnal Riset Ekonomi, Manajemen, Bisnis dan Akuntansi* 1 (4).
- Prawiranegara, B. 2018. Analisis Metode Pengakuan Pendapatan Konstruksi Pada Perusahaan Jasa Konstruksi. *Jurnal Wawasan dan Riset Akuntansi* 3 (2):81-92.
- Rudianto, E. 2013. *Akuntansi Manajemen Informasi Untuk Pengambilan Keputusan Strategis*. Jakarta: Erlangga.
- Setiawan, A. 2014. ANALISIS PENGAKUAN PENDAPATAN DAN PENGARUHNYA TERHADAP LABA USAHA PADA PERUSAHAAN KONSTRUKSI CV. PALER A INDAH.
- Sugiyono, P. D. 2013. *Metode penelitian manajemen*. Bandung: Alfabeta, CV.
- Suwardjono, S. 2011. *Teori akuntansi perekayasaan pelaporan keuangan*: Yogyakarta: BPFE Yogyakarta.
- Yevdokimova, M., V. Zamylnskyi, E. Kuznietsov, O. Sakovska, and H. Anatolii. 2018. EVOLUTION OF SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY APPLIED TO THE CONCEPT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT: MAINSTREAM OF THE 20 TH CENTURY. *Journal of Security & Sustainability Issues* 8 (1).

APPENDIX

Table 1. Total Income, Expenses, and Profits on the Income Statement per Month for 2019

	This Month	Recognized in Previous Month	Recognize in <i>n</i> month
September			
Revenue	Rp. 2.025.482.643,43		Rp. 2.025.482.643,43
Expense	Rp. 1.620.386.114,74		Rp. 1.620.386.114,74
Profits	Rp. 405.096.528,69		Rp. 405.096.528,69
Rounded			Rp. 405.096.000,00
October			
Revenue	Rp. 4.055.151.898,36	Rp. 2.025.482.643,43	Rp. 2.029.669.254,93
Expense	Rp. 3.244.121.518,69	Rp. 1.620.386.114,74	Rp. 1.623.735.403,94
Profits	Rp. 811.030.379,67	Rp. 405.096.528,69	Rp. 405.933.850,99
Rounded			Rp. 405.933.000,00
November			
Revenue	Rp. 7.290.565.265,13	Rp. 4.055.151.898,36	Rp. 3.235.413.366,77
Expense	Rp. 5.832.452.212,10	Rp. 3.244.121.518,69	Rp. 2.588.330.693,42
Profits	Rp. 1.458.113.053,03	Rp. 811.030.379,67	Rp. 647.082.673,35
Rounded			Rp. 647.082.000,00
December			
Revenue	Rp. 8.373.222.998,89	Rp. 7.290.565.265,13	Rp. 1.082.657.733,76
Expense	Rp. 6.698.578.399,11	Rp. 5.832.452.212,10	Rp. 866.126.187,00
Profits	Rp. 1.674.644.599,78	Rp. 1.458.113.053,03	Rp. 216.531.546,75
Rounded			Rp. 216.531.000,00